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Socializing Problem Solvers
Why the Technocratic Paradigm still dominates Sustainability Engineering Education.

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INTRODUCTION

The technological advances since the industrial revolution have brought prosperity, longevity, abundance and warded off plagues and famines but they have also allowed the unabated extraction of natural resources with little consideration for their renewability or the fair distribution of the economic proceeds of this extraction. As such, humanity is threatened by climate change, plastic pollution, the mass extinction of species, the depletion of critical natural resources, whilst at the same time dealing with increasing wealth inequality and mass human migration that is destabilizing political systems. Such a problem we have labelled a *sustainability* problem. If left unaddressed, it threatens the liberal democratic order and its capitalist economic foundation. Yet the complex economic, social and environmental interlinkages of the sustainability problem are only slowly starting to be addressed by social sciences disciplines such as political sciences, development studies, and economics among others. In the engineering disciplines, the situation depends very much on which discipline one looks at. In disciplines that are further from “core” engineering, like planning, design, mediology etc. new programmes are being developed which offer an interdisciplinary, pedagogically innovative approach to the subject. In the “core” disciplines of civil, mechanical, electric and chemical engineering, there is a general recognition that a paradigm shift away from a technical, disciplinary focus is needed. However, practice shows that sustainability has been integrated more at the disciplinary level, where it has been integrated at all.

So whilst “core” engineering education remains wedded to a disciplinary, technical view of the world, not all engineers are technocrats, and not all engineering education programmes socialise technocratic problem-solvers. We must apologize to engineers and engineering educators from hereon for using the term “engineers” to refer to the median engineer, who has undergone his education in a median engineering school with median didactics. That median engineer may be a bit of a caricature of himself: the drawback of a conceptual paper is that it tends to deal in simplified categories with somewhat less sensitivity to the subtle variations offered by reality. The simplified models developed by conceptual papers are meant to be tested and refined by empirical work. Please bear with the author, the empirical work is in progress. The purpose of this conceptual paper is to ask some fundamental questions about identity and sustainability that we believe to be interesting and timely in engineering education today, and to suggest some unusual answers that could be tested and refined against empirical evidence.

Let us consider our conceptual median engineer: he likes to solve problems - that is what he has been educated to do, and solving problems is part of what makes him an engineer, the two go hand in hand, almost like dictionary definitions of each other. But he was not always an engineer - he was once a child, and then a teenager whose friends have become lawyers, artists, bankers, shop owners etc. He may have had a proclivity for solving problems from an early age, but at some point, he went from being a young adult to being an engineer. He *professionalised*. You could argue that this happens progressively over an entire career; these things are ongoing processes. But they definitely have a starting point, which is the moment the high schooler decides that he wants to study engineering and goes to study at a university or a vocational school (the difference between the two is exactly one of those subtle variations of reality that needs to be refined empirically but which for the sake of a conceptual paper will be simplified as “engineering education”). What the high schooler goes through at university is a process of *socialisation* - he develops what the sociologist Anthony Giddens (1991) called a new *self-identity*, a new way of thinking about himself, a new lens through which to see himself within the world. Much research has been done from a social psychology perspective about the differences between personal, social and human identity. However, in this paper we are looking at self-identity from a phenomenological ontological perspective, the focus of which is on the person’s experience from the inside-out, even if that experience is located within a group, profession or surrounding. What we will

argue in this paper is that the lens through which engineering students construct their self-narrative makes the world appear full of specific problems that can be solved using man-made constructions that we shall call broadly by the Heideggerian term *modern technology*. This is another large throwing-together of constructions that vary from space rockets to mobile phone apps, but the reason we make it so large is that this is the aggregation made by Martin Heidegger (1977), whose analysis underpins the sociological approach of Giddens. This should not stop us from critiquing Heidegger's amalgamation when we discuss its implications.

The key question guiding our inquiry is situated within the field of engineering education, and beckons us towards a theoretical examination of the relationship between the development of engineering self-identity and sustainability as it unfolds around technology throughout the learning process of the engineering student. The task of this conceptual paper is as follows: first, we will try to open up the black box of engineering education to propose a theory of how engineering students are socialized as problem-solvers. Then, we will suggest that the issue of sustainability offers an existential challenge to engineering identity, and offer an interpretation of what might be causing the technocratic response to such a challenge. Finally, we will look at two educational approaches that could trigger a different response to sustainability issues in engineering students.

1 THE DOMINANCE OF THE TECHNOCRATIC PARADIGM

1.1 Late modernity and the special role of engineers

Giddens (1991) defined the age that we live in as *late modernity*, which is a continuation of *modernity* in the information age. The name "modernity" is shorthand for the set of institutions that shape society in the post-enlightenment era. The features of this epoch are the dominance of Capitalism as a mode of social and economic organisation, the importance of material power (wealth) in social relations, the possibility of total war given by destructive technologies, and the possibility of an Orwellian society given by surveillance technologies. These features make modernity both the most prosperous and the most dangerous time for mankind: we live in what Beck (1992) called the "risk society". To temper the risk of nuclear annihilation and Big Brother surveillance, we've put in place organisations and institutions whose job it is to reflect on society and to feed those reflections back into how we live our lives. This is why Giddens calls *late modernity* a *reflexive* period of time. In *late modernity*, globalization dominates, and the risks and the reflexivity are planetary.

In such a context, expert skills are pulled out of their local context and catapulted into global expert systems which provide the technical knowledge in a particular area for the whole world. Giddens calls this the "dialectic of the global and the local": nobody who chooses to live in society can opt out of these expert systems, everyone depends on them for the most basic functioning of their life. For instance, I don't question how my computer or the internet works every time I want to check my email: I am blindly reliant on the experts who designed them. Despite this, trust in experts, which was so high in the 20th Century, is wavering in the 21st Century: economists failed to predict the 2008 financial crisis; political experts failed to predict the return of populism; sociological experts failed to raise the alarm about mounting inequality... Remarkably, engineers seem almost immune to this critique. And whilst even bio-scientists, physicists and climate scientists are being dismissed by an increasing cohort of people, there are no widely circulating "alternative facts" about the tenets of the engineering profession. Why is this?

To understand why the engineer is special, we must go back to Heidegger. Heidegger argued that *modern technology* was different from anything that had preceded it in that it caused people to see the whole world around them not as nature, but instead as a stockpile

of energy and resources waiting to be extracted for the production of commodities ("standing-reserve" or *Bestand*). Heidegger unfortunately failed to link this explicitly to Capitalism as an extractive system, but this oversight was fixed by Giddens. The pivotal role of modern technology in every aspect of modernity has bestowed upon engineers a special role: they are the people tasked with what Heidegger called "enframing" (*Gestell*) the world. *Enframing* means performatively seeing the world as resources ready to be used for production. Enframing is one way to "reveal" the World, to open it up to human understanding. For example, the engineer looks at a river and reveals it to be a potential place to build a dam for the production of hydro-current. He finds a tree and reveals it as a source of wood pulp from which paper can be produced. There are other ways to reveal the world - through art, for instance - but modern technology only makes us see world as something that can be used in production. The engineer enframes the World because of his special position as the maker of the technology. Thanks to his intervention, the world becomes enframed for the rest of society. It may be that I walk through the forest and see nothing but trees, but that is not the point: everything I do is predicated on the world having been enframed as a standing-reserve. I would not be here at this conference by any other means since the aircraft that I took to get here and the fuel that it burned to bring me here required the enframing of the natural world as a resource.

Now we come to the advent of technocratic thinking and technocracies. With the engineers being endowed with such a special role in late modernity, how those engineers think and work is of paramount importance for the reflexive process of this "risk" society. Therefore, how engineering students are educated to become engineers is of the uttermost importance. So why does the technocratic paradigm dominate engineering education, and what consequence does this have for late modern society?

1.2 Existential Anxiety and Technocratic Thinking

Being human is a wondrous and frightening experience: we are the only animals capable of deeply reflecting on our own existence (that we know of). When any human stops to consider his own existence deeply, there are five big questions that remain unanswered: what is this strange thing that I experience as "being" (*existence*)? What is this World around me that I seem to be a part of but separate from (*the World*)? Why am I going to die, and what does that mean (*finitude*)? Who are all of these other people whose inner being I can never experience for myself (*others*)? Who am I (*self-identity*)? Giddens calls these "existential questions", a term he borrowed from a long-standing tradition of existentialist philosophy. The starting point existentialism is that we experience existence as a deeply troubling phenomenon. Just thinking about the questions we have listed, you have probably felt a sense of unease. These are not questions any human normally enjoys thinking about because to think about your own death or about the very fragile construction of identity that is "you" causes anxiety and feels like standing in front of an "abyss" according to Heidegger. This is a general human experience, and there are general human coping mechanisms for dealing with anxiety. Our best coping strategy is building reassuring everyday *routines* (this means little actions that we perform and repeat on a daily basis) and rituals, the essence of which we don't question on a regular basis and therefore provides us with *ontological security* (this means having a firm and safe sense of who we are). In traditional societies these routines and rituals are often grounded in religion and strict social structure. In late modernity, these routines and rituals are built around complex codes of social interaction and action that, if you think about it, wouldn't take much effort at all to disrupt. A recent sale on Nutella in French supermarkets caused all social codes to fly out of the window as people began brawling down the shopping aisles. As I said: it doesn't take much... But even to stop and think about how fragile our complex social system is causes anxiety.

Now try asking an engineer about existential questions - the most common answer I got when conducting some preliminary interview research for this paper was something like an uncomfortable shuffle, a puzzled look, "we don't think like that, we solve problems". When asked why, this was usually followed by "because that's how we're trained". So, engineering education builds into its socialisation process a set of routines and rituals which can be summarized as "problem-solving". These routines focus on training a pathway from a problem situation to a (usually technical) solution that bypasses existential questions. Thus, epistemological and ontological questions being deliberately ignored, the result is a problem-solving attitude grounded in a positivist view of science, in which problems and solutions are neither considered contentious nor subject to hermeneutic tensions. *Ipsa facto*, this generates a technocratic approach to problems. The technical solution-searching process is possibly the strongest antidote to existential anxiety known to man in late modernity, and it has spread beyond engineering, a point we will come back to in the next section. Note that this solution does not always clearly identify a problem to which it is the answer - that does not strictly matter in order to ward off existential anxiety. What matters is the act of daily solution-development grounded in a reassuringly materialist approach to the world that conveniently circumvents existential questions by assuming existence to be a pure physical fact. Why is the technical solution-searching process so good at this, and why are engineers so prone to it?

To answer this, we turn once again to Heidegger, who explained that it is the essence of technology itself to provide us with an escape from the emptiness of anxiety. Heidegger tells us is that the technician's gaze entrals us into busying ourselves with the smaller question of "beings" (things, people, places) rather than the larger and frightening question of Being (ontology). Thus, in busying ourselves with beings, we are worked up into a trance of production and consumption that has no other purpose than the activity of production and consumption itself, and staves off "real" thinking about Being. Heidegger warned against people who try to push away from the "Abyss of Being" by hiding behind the routine and mundane existence of beings. Giddens is not so judgemental, but does recognize the enthralling, all-encompassing nature of such frenetic activity as is directed by late modernity, capitalism and its technological systems. Engineers being the experts tasked with the design and production of technology in late modernity, it stands to reason that they are the most deeply involved in the cycle of activity described by Heidegger, and therefore the most deeply embedded in the production of routines that come with it. Such routines, grounded in materialism, lead to a reductionist, technocratic approach to complex problems. Adding the analysis of Giddens to that of Heidegger, these routines become a part of engineering self-identity. To be a part of the expert system of engineers, one must embrace the routines and rituals of the profession, and the place where these are developed is in engineering education. Is this a problem? Why can't we be happy with our technocratic engineers as they are? The reason is primarily that the sustainability problem has torn open the black box of engineering routines, rushing existential questions back into a discipline from which they had been banished. The answers that engineers give to these questions now may well determine how we collectively fair with sustaining our lifestyles in the coming decades, and perhaps even centuries.

2 THE SUSTAINABILITY PROBLEM OF ENGINEERING EDUCATION

2.1 Sustainability and Existential Anxiety

Calls for fundamentally rethinking the unsustainable practices of consumer capitalism have been echoing through academia and environmentalist movements since the 1960s. In the 21st Century, it has become clear that sustainability issues are not a question for distant future generations, but that a paradigm shift in our approach to the society-nature relationship is necessary right now. Sterling (1999) has called this paradigm shift a move towards "strong" sustainability, which requires to rethink capitalism and its modes of operation. However, our increasing awareness of the problem has yet to crystallize into

action. According to Huckle (2009), this delay can be explained by the strictures that capitalism places around modern life - requiring “economic growth or capital accumulations (with) an inbuilt tendency to discount present and future environmental costs”. At the same time, Huckle says, the power of the State to actively steer society towards a sustainable mode of living has been systematically undercut by powerful business interests as well as by the electoral imperatives of political parties. Thus, despite repeated and increasingly urgent calls for a paradigm shift and the dire warnings about what could happen should we fail to shift, we keep our efforts within a technocratic, technocentric, materialistic and reductionist approach within the consumer capitalist paradigm (Sterling, 2009). This can be summarized as “technology will solve it” - fanciful thinking about clean coal, carbon extraction processes, bio-engineering flora and fauna to ward off their imminent destruction through habitat loss and climate change, the list goes on. At the same time, fantasies about eternal “green growth” abound, systematically failing to challenge the dominant GDP-growth obsession and ignoring the basic maths behind the exponential function. The standard tenet of the technocratic approach is, as Gough and Scott (2007) explain, to have “confidence in the ability of human beings to develop scientific and technological solutions to environmental problems as they emerge”. Enter engineers, stage left, thrust into the spotlight as the saviours of humanity by politicians, business leaders and the general public alike.

Looking at the sustainability crisis within the theoretical framework that we have previously established, the impending environmental collapse is forcing us to confront ourselves with the existential anxiety that the frenzy of production and consumption mandated by capitalism was meant to obscure. The question of self-identity in the context of the sustainability crisis is particularly thorny: to think meaningfully about the sustainability crisis is to recognize the role that each one of us plays in the system from which the crisis emerges, the limitations of human possibilities that will necessarily flow from the maintenance of the system as it is, and the return of death and finitude as a prominent features of a world in which there is not food, water, shelter, or resources enough for everyone. An authentic confrontation with the anxiety produced by such realizations would force us to examine the destructive character of our everyday routines, thus breaking the safety cocoon of our self-identity. Most of us are not willing to engage with this, and prefer to imagine an army of engineers ready to produce the technology that will fix the problem and allow our mode of living to continue untroubled. Perhaps this partially explains the frenetic race for developing STEM education, often at the expense of humanities and social sciences. The engineer’s self-identity as a technical solution-searcher is reaffirmed by the expectations placed upon him by public discourse. It provides ontological security and alleviates the existential question of identity. He therefore has no incentive to deviate from this discourse.

2.2 The Dangers of Technocratic Thinking about Sustainability in Engineering Education

There is just one problem with this discourse: the technocratic approach doesn’t work because it always plays catch-up, attempting to solve problems without investigating their structural source, often long after lasting or permanent damage has already been caused, and very often without any regard for the misdistribution of the ill effects it might cause, predominantly borne by the poorest people on the planet. Nothing but a complete, fundamental rethink of society’s *modus operandi* will enable action in time to avoid a poor, nasty and brutish future (to paraphrase Hobbes) for the vast majority of humanity. And yet, by design, as part of the socialization process, engineering education reinforces the prominence of problem-solving routines in the self-identity formation of students. The closer one gets to “core” engineering, the stronger the technical approach. Yet even civil and mechanical engineers cannot ignore sustainability issues today - neither do they attempt to, but they tend to teach sustainability as a technical problem concerned only with the environment, without much input from the social sciences and humanities. It should be

emphasized that this is not the case in all engineering programmes, and the more one veers away from core engineering and towards planning, mediation etc., the more sustainability issues are embedded within a broader, interdisciplinary, reflexive view. But we have reason to believe that the problem-solving approach to sustainability dominates in the vast majority of core engineering programmes around the world. *A priori*, the very learning methods by which students are socialized into the engineering identity cannot generate any other approach. For instance, a teacher in manufacturing processes, who has himself been socialized as an engineer at university and later in his professional life, will teach, guide and evaluate his students in such a way as to encourage them to develop identities that reflect his own self-identity back at him, thus comforting his own self-narrative and stave off existential questions. Thus the more teacher-driven the method of learning, the stronger the teacher's hold on the development of students' self-narratives and routines, the stronger the technocratic approach.

To disrupt the formation of a technocratic way of thinking in engineering students, they must be confronted with a broader set of existential possibilities, and made aware of the contingent nature of the routines and narratives which they build. Such an awareness would allow for a more authentic confrontation with the systemic nature of the sustainability crisis. Such authenticity requires of the individual that he be willing to experience existential anxiety, and be willing to radically change his self-identity and the actions that he takes if the situation calls for it. Such is the call issued by the current state of collapse of our socio-economic-environmental system. The traditional learning system of engineering students must therefore be disrupted. This is a point also made by Sterling (1999) who argues that in order to generate meaningful change, education needs to be transformative rather than transmissive - and this means, among other things, switching the learning experience of students from a problem-solving approach to a problem-reframing process.

3 USING PROBLEMS TO CONFRONT ENGINEERING STUDENTS

3.1 Problem-oriented project-work as existential confrontation

The good news is that there is no need to reinvent the pedagogical wheel. Disruptive pedagogies already exist - indeed most of them are historically grounded in one way or another in existentialism. These pedagogies have been called problem-posing education (Freire, 1968 / 2000), exemplary learning (Negt, 1971), problem-based learning (Schmidt, 1983) and participant-directed, problem-oriented learning (Pedersen, 2008), among others.

In engineering education, project work has been around for a long time. The term "project" refers to a means of organising the learning process, but it says very little about its underlying purpose. Most project-based teaching in engineering education makes use of *task-based* projects, which are strongly teacher-driven and focus on finding a solution to narrowly defined technical problems; and highly structured *disciplinary projects* that are equally teacher-driven and focus on closed problems within the confines of the disciplinary boundaries of the subject in question (De Graaff & Kolmos, 2007). These kinds of projects, while useful for spurring student interest and contextualizing theoretical knowledge, in fact reinforce the routine-building process by comforting engineering students into a narrow framework of knowledge application. Students are encouraged to transpose the problem-solving *methods* that they acquire in these projects to the different contexts that they encounter in their career. However, since advances in cognitive sciences have taught us that problem-solving is entirely contingent on the knowledge-base from which it draws, what these projects are unwittingly accomplishing is entrenching the future problem-solving possibilities of students within the set disciplinary paradigm that they learn at university. Future professional problems that confront engineers will then be read within the disciplinary framework that they have developed during their education. Thus, it is not sufficient for learning to be "active" in order for it to be disruptive. Learning must be a process of authentic confrontation with a problem that forces the issue of self-identity back onto the table.

There is however a setting in which project-work can become disruptive to the engineering's student socialised problem-solving self-identity: when the projects are genuinely *problem-based*. Pedersen (2008) differentiates problem-based project work from other types in that a genuinely problem-based project has no known solution and no defined disciplinary boundary, but instead engages students in a dialectic research process in which the cooperation / conflict nexus builds around the institution, the supervisors, the project group members and the outside world. There are two features of truly problem-based project work that can actively disrupt the students' self-identity formation process: the dialectic process and exemplarity.

The dialectic process in the context of problem-based education was best described by Freire (1968) as the dialogue between the self and the other that makes the existence of the self contingent on its encounter with the other, and the confers product of the encounter emergent properties with the power to (re)shape the social world. Thus the co-operation and confrontation process described by Pedersen acquires the power to challenge the nascent self-identity of the engineering student when it crystallises around external actors who pull the students away from discipline-bound solutions, break the routines-in-formation and expose students to new viewpoints and power dynamics that scrape the coating of ontological security provided by the engineering classroom and expose them to existential questioning. However, exposing engineering students to the dialectic process without proper safeguards is likely to yield existential anxiety, spurring a retrenchment towards technocratic thinking. One means by which such anxiety can be managed is through the use of *exemplary* problem-formulations.

Exemplarity is a concept developed by Negt (1971) in the context of German working class education. Negt rejected the possibility of acquiring interdisciplinary thinking through disciplinary studies, and argued instead that students should consider problems with their own societal reality as a starting point and springboard to comes to grips with broader societal questions. In Negt's view, this would foster the possibility for social (and political) action. In other words, exemplarity offers an outlet for an authentic confrontation with a problem, the outcome of which shifts the paradigm of action from the disciplinary and technological to the interdisciplinary and societal. Such action is no longer "meaningless" as Heidegger stated, but deeply meaningful.

Both the dialectic process and exemplarity require that the students go through a confrontational problem-identification and problem-formulation process, as described by Holgaard, Guerra, Kolmos and Petersen (2017). This process is time-consuming and takes students from an open theme, to a problem area, then to a problem-formulation which needs to be stated and restated as the dialectic unfolds. Specifically, we submit that the dialectic confrontation happens in the stage of problem analysis that occurs between the problem-identification and problem-formulation phase of the project-work. Exemplarity is only possible when the problem field is mapped to include both the students and societal actors as stakeholders and the starting point of the problem-formulation process, rather than a side-idea to be entertained in the beginning of the research process then promptly discarded once a technological "solution" appears.

3.2 Resistance to genuine problem-based learning in engineering education

There are multiple reasons why, despite the sixty years of existence of problem-based project work, there has been no substantial shift in the paradigm of engineering education, even when society looks to the engineering professions for solutions to the sustainability crisis. Dialectics and exemplarity are difficult concepts to grasp. Truly coming to grips with these ideas challenges ontological security. If this is something difficult to ask of students

whose self-identity is still in formation, it is quasi-impossible to ask of engineering teachers, whose self-identity has been coagulating around the technological solution-seeker narrative for substantially longer. It comes as little surprise that when problem-oriented project work was introduced at Aalborg University in 1974, the greatest resistance came from the engineering teachers who wrote letters to the Rector demanding the return of traditional pedagogy. However, as a full return to lectures was not possible, engineering teachers at Aalborg have instead delayed students' exposure to truly problem-oriented project work by introducing task-based projects in the early years of their engineering education (Servant & Spliid, 2017). Thus it can be surmised that by the time students are exposed to problem-based projects in the later years of their bachelor education, their self-identity has already been shaped to a large extent by disciplinary perspectives and the problem-solving narratives that develop around task-based projects. The extent to which problem-based projects have been able to challenge students' ontological security has been further diminished by the introduction of a host of disciplinary courses alongside the project work, whereas half of the courses used to relate directly to the project work (reference). Given that this has happened in one of the best-practice institutions for problem-based project work in engineering education, one can only surmise the possibilities for genuine problem-orientation is engineering curricula worldwide.

CONCLUSION

This conceptual paper has tried to explain why the technocratic paradigm dominates the engineering profession by locating its starting point within the socialisation process of engineering students as they go through their education. Using insights from the philosophy of Heidegger and the sociology of Giddens, we have tried to show that the dominance of the technocratic paradigm stems from the particular role of technology in late modernity, and the special role that engineers play with regards to technology in that system. We have described technocratic thinking as a coping mechanism that provides ontological security against existential anxiety. We have then explained how the sustainability crisis threatens that ontological security, to which the response is to extend technocratic thinking in engineering education to sustainability issues. We have then proposed a means by which engineering education can counter technocratic thinking, by using problem-based project work that is both dialectic and exemplary.

In conclusion, we would like to remark that the possibilities for opening engineering education up to a paradigm shift on sustainability already exist. The pedagogy which could be used has already been described, but is just not applied, particularly in "core" engineering subjects. We hope that we have succeeded in opening a dialogue with engineering educators on the role of existential questions and ontological security in defining how engineering education socialises students; and through these reflections, pave the way for a renewal of interest in dialectic and exemplary problem-based methods of educating engineers.

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